

Interval-valued neutrosophic competition graphs

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ABSTRACT. We first introduce the concept of interval-valued neutrosophic competition graphs. We then discuss certain types, including k -competition interval-valued neutrosophic graphs, p -competition interval-valued neutrosophic graphs and m -step interval-valued neutrosophic competition graphs. Moreover, we present the concept of m -step interval-valued neutrosophic neighbourhood graphs.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In 1975, Zadeh [35] introduced the notion of interval-valued fuzzy sets as an extension of fuzzy sets [34] in which the values of the membership degrees are intervals of numbers instead of the numbers. Interval-valued fuzzy sets provide a more adequate description of uncertainty than traditional fuzzy sets. It is therefore important to use interval-valued fuzzy sets in applications, such as fuzzy control. One of the computationally most intensive part of fuzzy control is defuzzification [19]. Atanassov [12] proposed the extended form of fuzzy set theory by adding a new component, called, intuitionistic fuzzy sets. Smarandache [26, 27] introduced the concept of neutrosophic sets by combining the non-standard analysis. In neutrosophic set, the membership value is associated with three components: truth-membership (t), indeterminacy-membership (i) and falsity-membership (f), in which each membership value is a real standard or non-standard subset of the non-standard unit interval $]0^-, 1^+[$ and there is no restriction on their sum. Smarandache [28] and Wang et al. [29] presented the notion of single-valued neutrosophic sets to apply neutrosophic sets in real life problems more conveniently. In single-valued neutrosophic sets, three components are independent and their values are taken from the standard unit interval $[0, 1]$. Wang et al. [30] presented the concept of interval-valued neutrosophic

sets, which is more precise and more flexible than the single-valued neutrosophic set. An interval-valued neutrosophic set is a generalization of the concept of single-valued neutrosophic set, in which three membership (t, i, f) functions are independent, and their values belong to the unit interval $[0, 1]$.

Kauffman [18] gave the definition of a fuzzy graph. Fuzzy graphs were narrated by Rosenfeld [22]. After that, some remarks on fuzzy graphs were represented by Bhattacharya [13]. He showed that all the concepts on crisp graph theory do not have similarities in fuzzy graphs. Wu [32] discussed fuzzy digraphs. The concept of fuzzy k -competition graphs and p -competition fuzzy graphs was first developed by Samanta and Pal in [23], it was further studied in [11, 21, 25]. Samanta et al. [24] introduced the generalization of fuzzy competition graphs, called m -step fuzzy competition graphs. Samanta et al. [24] also introduced the concepts of fuzzy m -step neighbourhood graphs, fuzzy economic competition graphs, and m -step economic competition graphs. The concepts of bipolar fuzzy competition graphs and intuitionistic fuzzy competition graphs are discussed in [21, 25]. Hongmei and Lianhua [16], gave definition of interval-valued fuzzy graphs. Akram et al. [1, 2, 3, 4] have introduced several concepts on interval-valued fuzzy graphs and interval-valued neutrosophic graphs. Akram and Shahzadi [6] introduced the notion of neutrosophic soft graphs with applications. Akram [7] introduced the notion of single-valued neutrosophic planar graphs. Akram and Shahzadi [8] studied properties of single-valued neutrosophic graphs by level graphs. Recently, Akram and Nasir [5] have discussed some concepts of interval-valued neutrosophic graphs. In this paper, we first introduce the concept of interval-valued neutrosophic competition graphs. We then discuss certain types, including k -competition interval-valued neutrosophic graphs, p -competition interval-valued neutrosophic graphs and m -step interval-valued neutrosophic competition graphs. Moreover, we present the concept of m -step interval-valued neutrosophic neighbourhood graphs.

We have used standard definitions and terminologies in this paper. For other notations, terminologies and applications not mentioned in the paper, the readers are referred to [6, 9, 10, 13, 14, 15, 17, 20, 26, 33, 36].

2. INTERVAL-VALUED NEUTROSOPHIC COMPETITION GRAPHS

Definition 2.1 ([35]). The interval-valued fuzzy set A in X is defined by

$$A = \{(s, [t_A^l(s), t_A^u(s)]) : s \in X\},$$

where, $t_A^l(s)$ and $t_A^u(s)$ are fuzzy subsets of X such that $t_A^l(s) \leq t_A^u(s)$ for all $x \in X$. An interval-valued fuzzy relation on X is an interval-valued fuzzy set B in $X \times X$.

Definition 2.2 ([30, 31]). The interval-valued neutrosophic set (IVN-set) A in X is defined by

$$A = \{(s, [t_A^l(s), t_A^u(s)], [i_A^l(s), i_A^u(s)], [f_A^l(s), f_A^u(s)]) : s \in X\},$$

where, $t_A^l(s)$, $t_A^u(s)$, $i_A^l(s)$, $i_A^u(s)$, $f_A^l(s)$, and $f_A^u(s)$ are neutrosophic subsets of X such that $t_A^l(s) \leq t_A^u(s)$, $i_A^l(s) \leq i_A^u(s)$ and $f_A^l(s) \leq f_A^u(s)$ for all $s \in X$. An interval-valued neutrosophic relation (IVN-relation) on X is an interval-valued neutrosophic set B in $X \times X$.

Definition 2.3 ([5]). An interval-valued neutrosophic digraph (IVN-digraph) on a non-empty set X is a pair $G = (A, \vec{B})$, (in short, G), where $A = ([t_A^l, t_A^u], [i_A^l, i_A^u], [f_A^l, f_A^u])$ is an IVN-set on X and $B = ([t_B^l, t_B^u], [i_B^l, i_B^u], [f_B^l, f_B^u])$ is an IVN-relation on X , such that:

- (i) $t_B^l(\overrightarrow{s, w}) \leq t_A^l(s) \wedge t_A^l(w)$, $t_B^u(\overrightarrow{s, w}) \leq t_A^u(s) \wedge t_A^u(w)$,
- (ii) $i_B^l(\overrightarrow{s, w}) \leq i_A^l(s) \wedge i_A^l(w)$, $i_B^u(\overrightarrow{s, w}) \leq i_A^u(s) \wedge i_A^u(w)$,
- (iii) $f_B^l(\overrightarrow{s, w}) \leq f_A^l(s) \wedge f_A^l(w)$, $f_B^u(\overrightarrow{s, w}) \leq f_A^u(s) \wedge f_A^u(w)$, for all $s, w \in X$.

Example 2.4. We construct an IVN-digraph $G = (A, \vec{B})$ on $X = \{a, b, c\}$ as shown in Fig. 1.

FIGURE 1. IVN-digraph

Definition 2.5. Let $\vec{G}$ be an IVN-digraph then interval-valued neutrosophic out-neighbourhoods (IVN-out-neighbourhoods) of a vertex s is an IVN-set

$$N^+(s) = (X_s^+, [t_s^{(l)+}, t_s^{(u)+}], [i_s^{(l)+}, i_s^{(u)+}], [f_s^{(l)+}, t_s^{(u)+}]),$$

where

$$X_s^+ = \{w | [t_B^l(\overrightarrow{s, w}) > 0, t_B^u(\overrightarrow{s, w}) > 0], [i_B^l(\overrightarrow{s, w}) > 0, i_B^u(\overrightarrow{s, w}) > 0], [f_B^l(\overrightarrow{s, w}) > 0, f_B^u(\overrightarrow{s, w}) > 0]\},$$

such that $t_s^{(l)+} : X_s^+ \rightarrow [0, 1]$, defined by $t_s^{(l)+}(w) = t_B^l(\overrightarrow{s, w})$, $t_s^{(u)+} : X_s^+ \rightarrow [0, 1]$, defined by $t_s^{(u)+}(w) = t_B^u(\overrightarrow{s, w})$, $i_s^{(l)+} : X_s^+ \rightarrow [0, 1]$, defined by $i_s^{(l)+}(w) = i_B^l(\overrightarrow{s, w})$, $i_s^{(u)+} : X_s^+ \rightarrow [0, 1]$, defined by $i_s^{(u)+}(w) = i_B^u(\overrightarrow{s, w})$, $f_s^{(l)+} : X_s^+ \rightarrow [0, 1]$, defined by $f_s^{(l)+}(w) = f_B^l(\overrightarrow{s, w})$, $f_s^{(u)+} : X_s^+ \rightarrow [0, 1]$, defined by $f_s^{(u)+}(w) = f_B^u(\overrightarrow{s, w})$.

Definition 2.6. Let $\vec{G}$ be an IVN-digraph then interval-valued neutrosophic in-neighbourhoods (IVN-in-neighbourhoods) of a vertex s is an IVN-set

$$N^-(s) = (X_s^-, [t_s^{(l)-}, t_s^{(u)-}], [i_s^{(l)-}, i_s^{(u)-}], [f_s^{(l)-}, t_s^{(u)-}]),$$

where

$$X_s^- = \{w | [t_B^l(\overrightarrow{w, s}) > 0, t_B^u(\overrightarrow{w, s}) > 0], [i_B^l(\overrightarrow{w, s}) > 0, i_B^u(\overrightarrow{w, s}) > 0], [f_B^l(\overrightarrow{w, s}) > 0, f_B^u(\overrightarrow{w, s}) > 0]\},$$

such that $t_s^{(l)-} : X_s^- \rightarrow [0, 1]$, defined by $t_s^{(l)-}(w) = t_B^l(\overrightarrow{w, s})$, $t_s^{(u)-} : X_s^- \rightarrow [0, 1]$, defined by $t_s^{(u)-}(w) = t_B^u(\overrightarrow{w, s})$, $i_s^{(l)-} : X_s^- \rightarrow [0, 1]$, defined by $i_s^{(l)-}(w) = i_B^l(\overrightarrow{w, s})$, $i_s^{(u)-} : X_s^- \rightarrow [0, 1]$, defined by $i_s^{(u)-}(w) = i_B^u(\overrightarrow{w, s})$, $f_s^{(l)-} : X_s^- \rightarrow [0, 1]$, defined by $f_s^{(l)-}(w) = f_B^l(\overrightarrow{w, s})$, $f_s^{(u)-} : X_s^- \rightarrow [0, 1]$, defined by $f_s^{(u)-}(w) = f_B^u(\overrightarrow{w, s})$.

Example 2.7. Consider an IVN-digraph $G = (A, \overrightarrow{B})$ on $X = \{a, b, c\}$ as shown in Fig. 2.

FIGURE 2. IVN-digraph

We have Table 1 and Table 2 representing interval-valued neutrosophic out and in-neighbourhoods, respectively.

TABLE 1. IVN-out-neighbourhoods

s	$\mathbb{N}^+(s)$
a	$\{(b, [0.1, 0.2], [0.2, 0.3], [0.1, 0.6]), (c, [0.1, 0.2], [0.1, 0.3], [0.2, 0.6])\}$
b	$\emptyset$
c	$\{(b, [0.1, 0.2], [0.2, 0.3], [0.2, 0.5])\}$

TABLE 2. IVN-in-neighbourhoods

s	$\mathbb{N}^-(s)$
a	$\emptyset$
b	$\{(a, [0.1, 0.2], [0.2, 0.3], [0.1, 0.6]), (c, [0.1, 0.2], [0.2, 0.3], [0.2, 0.5])\}$
c	$\{(a, [0.1, 0.2], [0.1, 0.3], [0.2, 0.6])\}$

Definition 2.8. The height of IVN-set $A = (s, [t_A^l, t_A^u], [i_A^l, i_A^u], [f_A^l, f_A^u])$ in universe of discourse X is defined as: for all $s \in X$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 h(A) &= ([h_1^l(A), h_1^u(A)], [h_2^l(A), h_2^u(A)], [h_3^l(A), h_3^u(A)]), \\
 &= ([\sup_{s \in X} t_A^l(s), \sup_{s \in X} t_A^u(s)], [\sup_{s \in X} i_A^l(s), \sup_{s \in X} i_A^u(s)], [\inf_{s \in X} f_A^l(s), \inf_{s \in X} f_A^u(s)]).
 \end{aligned}$$

Definition 2.9. An interval-valued neutrosophic competition graph (IVNC-graph) of an interval-valued neutrosophic graph (IVN-graph) $\vec{G} = (A, \vec{B})$ is an undirected IVN-graph $\mathbb{C}(\vec{G}) = (A, W)$ which has the same vertex set as in $\vec{G}$ and there is an edge between two vertices s and w if and only if $\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w) \neq \emptyset$. The truth-membership, indeterminacy-membership and falsity-membership values of the edge (s, w) are defined as: for all $s, w \in X$,

- (i) $t_W^l(s, w) = (t_A^l(s) \wedge t_A^l(w))h_1^l(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))$,
 $t_W^u(s, w) = (t_A^u(s) \wedge t_A^u(w))h_1^u(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))$,
- (ii) $i_W^l(s, w) = (i_A^l(s) \wedge i_A^l(w))h_2^l(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))$,
 $i_W^u(s, w) = (i_A^u(s) \wedge i_A^u(w))h_2^u(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))$,
- (iii) $f_W^l(s, w) = (f_A^l(s) \wedge f_A^l(w))h_3^l(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))$,
 $f_W^u(s, w) = (f_A^u(s) \wedge f_A^u(w))h_3^u(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))$.

Example 2.10. Consider an IVN-digraph $G = (A, \vec{B})$ on $X = \{a, b, c\}$ as shown in Fig. 3.

FIGURE 3. IVN-digraph

We have Table 3 and Table 4 representing interval-valued neutrosophic out and in-neighbourhoods, respectively.

TABLE 3. IVN-out-neighbourhoods

s	$\mathbb{N}^+(s)$
a	$\{(b, [0.1, 0.2], [0.2, 0.3], [0.1, 0.6]), (c, [0.1, 0.2], [0.1, 0.3], [0.2, 0.6])\}$
b	$\emptyset$
c	$\{(b, [0.1, 0.2], [0.2, 0.3], [0.2, 0.5])\}$

TABLE 4. IVN-in-neighbourhoods

s	$\mathbb{N}^-(s)$
a	$\emptyset$
b	$\{(a, [0.1, 0.2], [0.2, 0.3], [0.1, 0.6]), (c, [0.1, 0.2], [0.2, 0.3], [0.2, 0.5])\}$
c	$\{(a, [0.1, 0.2], [0.1, 0.3], [0.2, 0.6])\}$

Then IVNC-graph of Fig. 3 is shown in Fig. 4.

FIGURE 4. IVNC-graph

Definition 2.11. Consider an IVN-graph $G = (A, B)$, where $A = ([A_1^l, A_1^u], [A_2^l, A_2^u], [A_3^l, A_3^u])$ and $B = ([B_1^l, B_1^u], [B_2^l, B_2^u], [B_3^l, B_3^u])$. then, an edge (s, w) , $s, w \in X$ is called independent strong, if

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2}[A_1^l(s) \wedge A_1^l(w)] &< B_1^l(s, w), & \frac{1}{2}[A_1^u(s) \wedge A_1^u(w)] &< B_1^u(s, w), \\ \frac{1}{2}[A_2^l(s) \wedge A_2^l(w)] &< B_2^l(s, w), & \frac{1}{2}[A_2^u(s) \wedge A_2^u(w)] &< B_2^u(s, w), \\ \frac{1}{2}[A_3^l(s) \wedge A_3^l(w)] &> B_3^l(s, w), & \frac{1}{2}[A_3^u(s) \wedge A_3^u(w)] &> B_3^u(s, w). \end{aligned}$$

Otherwise, it is called weak.

We state the following theorems without their proofs.

Theorem 2.12. Suppose $\vec{G}$ is an IVN-digraph. If $\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w)$ contains only one element of $\vec{G}$, then the edge (s, w) of $\mathbb{C}(\vec{G})$ is independent strong if and only if

$$\begin{aligned} |[\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w)]|_{t^l} &> 0.5, & |[\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w)]|_{t^u} &> 0.5, \\ |[\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w)]|_{i^l} &> 0.5, & |[\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w)]|_{i^u} &> 0.5, \\ |[\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w)]|_{f^l} &< 0.5, & |[\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w)]|_{f^u} &< 0.5. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2.13. If all the edges of an IVN-digraph $\vec{G}$ are independent strong, then

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{B_1^l(s, w)}{(A_1^l(s) \wedge A_1^l(w))^2} &> 0.5, & \frac{B_1^u(s, w)}{(A_1^u(s) \wedge A_1^u(w))^2} &> 0.5, \\ \frac{B_2^l(s, w)}{(A_2^l(s) \wedge A_2^l(w))^2} &> 0.5, & \frac{B_2^u(s, w)}{(A_2^u(s) \wedge A_2^u(w))^2} &> 0.5, \\ \frac{B_3^l(s, w)}{(A_3^l(s) \wedge A_3^l(w))^2} &< 0.5, & \frac{B_3^u(s, w)}{(A_3^u(s) \wedge A_3^u(w))^2} &< 0.5, \end{aligned}$$

for all edges (s, w) in $\mathbb{C}(\vec{G})$.

Definition 2.14. The interval-valued neutrosophic open-neighbourhood (IVN-open-neighbourhood) of a vertex s of an IVN-graph $G = (A, B)$ is IVN-set $\mathbb{N}(s) = (X_s, [t_s^l, t_s^u], [i_s^l, i_s^u], [f_s^l, f_s^u])$, where

$$X_s = \{w | [B_1^l(s, w) > 0, B_1^u(s, w) > 0], [B_2^l(s, w) > 0, B_2^u(s, w) > 0], [B_3^l(s, w) > 0, B_3^u(s, w) > 0]\},$$

and $t_s^l : X_s \rightarrow [0, 1]$ defined by $t_s^l(w) = B_1^l(s, w)$, $t_s^u : X_s \rightarrow [0, 1]$ defined by $t_s^u(w) = B_1^u(s, w)$, $i_s^l : X_s \rightarrow [0, 1]$ defined by $i_s^l(w) = B_2^l(s, w)$, $i_s^u : X_s \rightarrow [0, 1]$ defined by $i_s^u(w) = B_2^u(s, w)$, $f_s^l : X_s \rightarrow [0, 1]$ defined by $f_s^l(w) = B_3^l(s, w)$, $f_s^u : X_s \rightarrow [0, 1]$ defined by $f_s^u(w) = B_3^u(s, w)$. For every vertex $s \in X$, the interval-valued neutrosophic singleton set, $A_s = (s, [A_1^l, A_1^u], [A_2^l, A_2^u], [A_3^l, A_3^u])$ such that: $A_1^l : \{s\} \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $A_1^u : \{s\} \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $A_2^l : \{s\} \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $A_2^u : \{s\} \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $A_3^l : \{s\} \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $A_3^u : \{s\} \rightarrow [0, 1]$, defined by $A_1^l(s) = A_1^l(s)$, $A_1^u(s) = A_1^u(s)$, $A_2^l(s) = A_2^l(s)$, $A_2^u(s) = A_2^u(s)$, $A_3^l(s) = A_3^l(s)$ and $A_3^u(s) = A_3^u(s)$, respectively. The interval-valued neutrosophic closed-neighbourhood (IVN-closed-neighbourhood) of a vertex s is $\mathbb{N}[s] = \mathbb{N}(s) \cup A_s$.

Definition 2.15. Suppose $G = (A, B)$ is an IVN-graph. Interval-valued neutrosophic open-neighbourhood graph (IVN-open-neighbourhood-graph) of G is an IVN-graph $\mathbb{N}(G) = (A, B')$ which has the same IVN-set of vertices in G and has an interval-valued neutrosophic edge between two vertices $s, w \in X$ in $\mathbb{N}(G)$ if and only if $\mathbb{N}(s) \cap \mathbb{N}(w)$ is a non-empty IVN-set in G . The truth-membership, indeterminacy-membership, falsity-membership values of the edge (s, w) are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} B_1^{ll}(s, w) &= [A_1^l(s) \wedge A_1^l(w)]h_1^l(\mathbb{N}(s) \cap \mathbb{N}(w)), \\ B_2^{ll}(s, w) &= [A_2^l(s) \wedge A_2^l(w)]h_2^l(\mathbb{N}(s) \cap \mathbb{N}(w)), \\ B_3^{ll}(s, w) &= [A_3^l(s) \wedge A_3^l(w)]h_3^l(\mathbb{N}(s) \cap \mathbb{N}(w)), \\ B_1^{uu}(s, w) &= [A_1^u(s) \wedge A_1^u(w)]h_1^u(\mathbb{N}(s) \cap \mathbb{N}(w)), \\ B_2^{uu}(s, w) &= [A_2^u(s) \wedge A_2^u(w)]h_2^u(\mathbb{N}(s) \cap \mathbb{N}(w)), \\ B_3^{uu}(s, w) &= [A_3^u(s) \wedge A_3^u(w)]h_3^u(\mathbb{N}(s) \cap \mathbb{N}(w)), \text{ respectively.} \end{aligned}$$

Definition 2.16. Suppose $G = (A, B)$ is an IVN-graph. Interval-valued neutrosophic closed-neighbourhood graph (IVN-closed-neighbourhood-graph) of G is an IVN-graph $\mathbb{N}[G] = (A, B')$ which has the same IVN-set of vertices in G and has an interval-valued neutrosophic edge between two vertices $s, w \in X$ in $\mathbb{N}[G]$ if and only if $\mathbb{N}[s] \cap \mathbb{N}[w]$ is a non-empty IVN-set in G . The truth-membership, indeterminacy-membership, falsity-membership values of the edge (s, w) are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} B_1^{ll}(s, w) &= [A_1^l(s) \wedge A_1^l(w)]h_1^l(\mathbb{N}[s] \cap \mathbb{N}[w]), \\ B_2^{ll}(s, w) &= [A_2^l(s) \wedge A_2^l(w)]h_2^l(\mathbb{N}[s] \cap \mathbb{N}[w]), \\ B_3^{ll}(s, w) &= [A_3^l(s) \wedge A_3^l(w)]h_3^l(\mathbb{N}[s] \cap \mathbb{N}[w]), \\ B_1^{uu}(s, w) &= [A_1^u(s) \wedge A_1^u(w)]h_1^u(\mathbb{N}[s] \cap \mathbb{N}[w]), \\ B_2^{uu}(s, w) &= [A_2^u(s) \wedge A_2^u(w)]h_2^u(\mathbb{N}[s] \cap \mathbb{N}[w]), \\ B_3^{uu}(s, w) &= [A_3^u(s) \wedge A_3^u(w)]h_3^u(\mathbb{N}[s] \cap \mathbb{N}[w]), \text{ respectively.} \end{aligned}$$

We now discuss the method of construction of interval-valued neutrosophic competition graph of the Cartesian product of IVN-digraph in following theorem which can be proof using similar method as used in [21], hence we omit its proof.

Theorem 2.17. Let $\mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_1) = (A_1, B_1)$ and $\mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_2) = (A_2, B_2)$ be two IVNC-graphs of IVN-digraphs $\vec{G}_1 = (A_1, \vec{L}_1)$ and $\vec{G}_2 = (A_2, \vec{L}_2)$, respectively. Then $\mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_1 \square \vec{G}_2) = G_{\mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_1)^* \square \mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_2)^*} \cup G^\square$, where $G_{\mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_1)^* \square \mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_2)^*}$ is an IVN-graph on the crisp graph $(X_1 \times X_2, E_{\mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_1)^* \square \mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_2)^*})$, $\mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_1)^*$ and $\mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_2)^*$ are the crisp competition graphs of $\vec{G}_1$ and $\vec{G}_2$, respectively. $G^\square$ is an IVN-graph on $(X_1 \times X_2, E^\square)$ such that:

- (1) $E^\square = \{(s_1, s_2)(w_1, w_2) : w_1 \in \mathbb{N}^-(s_1)^*, w_2 \in \mathbb{N}^+(s_2)^*\}$
 $E_{\mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_1)^* \square \mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_2)^*} = \{(s_1, s_2)(s_1, w_2) : s_1 \in X_1, s_2 w_2 \in E_{\mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_2)^*}\}$
 $\cup \{(s_1, s_2)(w_1, s_2) : s_2 \in X_2, s_1 w_1 \in E_{\mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_1)^*}\}$.
- (2) $t_{A_1 \square A_2}^l = t_{A_1}^l(s_1) \wedge t_{A_2}^l(s_2), \quad i_{A_1 \square A_2}^l = i_{A_1}^l(s_1) \wedge i_{A_2}^l(s_2), \quad f_{A_1 \square A_2}^l = f_{A_1}^l(s_1) \wedge f_{A_2}^l(s_2),$
 $t_{A_1 \square A_2}^u = t_{A_1}^u(s_1) \wedge t_{A_2}^u(s_2), \quad i_{A_1 \square A_2}^u = i_{A_1}^u(s_1) \wedge i_{A_2}^u(s_2), \quad f_{A_1 \square A_2}^u = f_{A_1}^u(s_1) \wedge f_{A_2}^u(s_2).$
- (3) $t_B^l((s_1, s_2)(s_1, w_2)) = [t_{A_1}^l(s_1) \wedge t_{A_2}^l(s_2) \wedge t_{A_2}^l(w_2)] \times \vee_{a_2} \{t_{A_1}^l(s_1) \wedge t_{\vec{L}_2}^l(s_2 a_2) \wedge t_{\vec{L}_2}^l(w_2 a_2)\},$
 $(s_1, s_2)(s_1, w_2) \in E_{\mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_1)^* \square \mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_2)^*}, \quad a_2 \in (\mathbb{N}^+(s_2) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w_2))^*.$
- (4) $i_B^l((s_1, s_2)(s_1, w_2)) = [i_{A_1}^l(s_1) \wedge i_{A_2}^l(s_2) \wedge i_{A_2}^l(w_2)] \times \vee_{a_2} \{i_{A_1}^l(s_1) \wedge i_{\vec{L}_2}^l(s_2 a_2) \wedge i_{\vec{L}_2}^l(w_2 a_2)\},$
 $(s_1, s_2)(s_1, w_2) \in E_{\mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_1)^* \square \mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_2)^*}, \quad a_2 \in (\mathbb{N}^+(s_2) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w_2))^*.$
- (5) $f_B^l((s_1, s_2)(s_1, w_2)) = [f_{A_1}^l(s_1) \wedge f_{A_2}^l(s_2) \wedge f_{A_2}^l(w_2)] \times \vee_{a_2} \{f_{A_1}^l(s_1) \wedge f_{\vec{L}_2}^l(s_2 a_2) \wedge f_{\vec{L}_2}^l(w_2 a_2)\},$
 $(s_1, s_2)(s_1, w_2) \in E_{\mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_1)^* \square \mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_2)^*}, \quad a_2 \in (\mathbb{N}^+(s_2) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w_2))^*.$
- (6) $t_B^u((s_1, s_2)(s_1, w_2)) = [t_{A_1}^u(s_1) \wedge t_{A_2}^u(s_2) \wedge t_{A_2}^u(w_2)] \times \vee_{a_2} \{t_{A_1}^u(s_1) \wedge t_{\vec{L}_2}^u(s_2 a_2) \wedge t_{\vec{L}_2}^u(w_2 a_2)\},$
 $(s_1, s_2)(s_1, w_2) \in E_{\mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_1)^* \square \mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_2)^*}, \quad a_2 \in (\mathbb{N}^+(s_2) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w_2))^*.$
- (7) $i_B^u((s_1, s_2)(s_1, w_2)) = [i_{A_1}^u(s_1) \wedge i_{A_2}^u(s_2) \wedge i_{A_2}^u(w_2)] \times \vee_{a_2} \{i_{A_1}^u(s_1) \wedge i_{\vec{L}_2}^u(s_2 a_2) \wedge i_{\vec{L}_2}^u(w_2 a_2)\},$
 $(s_1, s_2)(s_1, w_2) \in E_{\mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_1)^* \square \mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_2)^*}, \quad a_2 \in (\mathbb{N}^+(s_2) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w_2))^*.$
- (8) $f_B^u((s_1, s_2)(s_1, w_2)) = [f_{A_1}^u(s_1) \wedge f_{A_2}^u(s_2) \wedge f_{A_2}^u(w_2)] \times \vee_{a_2} \{f_{A_1}^u(s_1) \wedge f_{\vec{L}_2}^u(s_2 a_2) \wedge f_{\vec{L}_2}^u(w_2 a_2)\},$
 $(s_1, s_2)(s_1, w_2) \in E_{\mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_1)^* \square \mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_2)^*}, \quad a_2 \in (\mathbb{N}^+(s_2) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w_2))^*.$
- (9) $t_B^l((s_1, s_2)(w_1, s_2)) = [t_{A_1}^l(s_1) \wedge t_{A_1}^l(w_1) \wedge t_{A_2}^l(s_2)] \times \vee_{a_1} \{t_{A_2}^l(s_2) \wedge t_{\vec{L}_1}^l(s_1 a_1) \wedge t_{\vec{L}_1}^l(w_1 a_1)\},$
 $(s_1, s_2)(w_1, s_2) \in E_{\mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_1)^* \square \mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_2)^*}, \quad a_1 \in (\mathbb{N}^+(s_1) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w_1))^*.$
- (10) $i_B^l((s_1, s_2)(w_1, s_2)) = [i_{A_1}^l(s_1) \wedge i_{A_1}^l(w_1) \wedge i_{A_2}^l(s_2)] \times \vee_{a_1} \{i_{A_2}^l(s_2) \wedge i_{\vec{L}_1}^l(s_1 a_1) \wedge i_{\vec{L}_1}^l(w_1 a_1)\},$
 $(s_1, s_2)(w_1, s_2) \in E_{\mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_1)^* \square \mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_2)^*}, \quad a_1 \in (\mathbb{N}^+(s_1) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w_1))^*.$

- (11) $f_B^l((s_1, s_2)(w_1, s_2)) = [f_{A_1}^l(s_1) \wedge f_{A_1}^l(w_1) \wedge f_{A_2}^l(s_2)] \times \vee_{a_1} \{t_{A_2}^l(s_2) \wedge f_{L_1}^l(s_1 a_1) \wedge f_{L_1}^l(w_1 a_1)\},$
 $(s_1, s_2)(w_1, s_2) \in E_{\mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_1)^*} \square E_{\mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_2)^*}, \quad a_1 \in (\mathbb{N}^+(s_1) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w_1))^*.$
- (12) $t_B^u((s_1, s_2)(w_1, s_2)) = [t_{A_1}^u(s_1) \wedge t_{A_1}^u(w_1) \wedge t_{A_2}^u(s_2)] \times \vee_{a_1} \{t_{A_2}^u(s_2) \wedge t_{L_1}^u(s_1 a_1) \wedge t_{L_1}^u(w_1 a_1)\},$
 $(s_1, s_2)(w_1, s_2) \in E_{\mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_1)^*} \square E_{\mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_2)^*}, \quad a_1 \in (\mathbb{N}^+(s_1) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w_1))^*.$
- (13) $i_B^u((s_1, s_2)(w_1, s_2)) = [i_{A_1}^u(s_1) \wedge i_{A_1}^u(w_1) \wedge i_{A_2}^u(s_2)] \times \vee_{a_1} \{i_{A_2}^u(s_2) \wedge i_{L_1}^u(s_1 a_1) \wedge i_{L_1}^u(w_1 a_1)\},$
 $(s_1, s_2)(w_1, s_2) \in E_{\mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_1)^*} \square E_{\mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_2)^*}, \quad a_1 \in (\mathbb{N}^+(s_1) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w_1))^*.$
- (14) $f_B^u((s_1, s_2)(w_1, s_2)) = [f_{A_1}^u(s_1) \wedge f_{A_1}^u(w_1) \wedge f_{A_2}^u(s_2)] \times \vee_{a_1} \{t_{A_2}^u(s_2) \wedge f_{L_1}^u(s_1 a_1) \wedge f_{L_1}^u(w_1 a_1)\},$
 $(s_1, s_2)(w_1, s_2) \in E_{\mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_1)^*} \square E_{\mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_2)^*}, \quad a_1 \in (\mathbb{N}^+(s_1) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w_1))^*.$
- (15) $t_B^l((s_1, s_2)(w_1, w_2)) = [t_{A_1}^l(s_1) \wedge t_{A_1}^l(w_1) \wedge t_{A_2}^l(s_2) \wedge t_{A_2}^l(w_2)] \times [t_{A_1}^l(s_1) \wedge t_{L_1}^l(w_1 s_1) \wedge t_{L_2}^l(w_2) \wedge t_{L_2}^l(s_2 w_2)],$
 $(s_1, w_1)(s_2, w_2) \in E^\square.$
- (16) $i_B^l((s_1, s_2)(w_1, w_2)) = [i_{A_1}^l(s_1) \wedge i_{A_1}^l(w_1) \wedge i_{A_2}^l(s_2) \wedge i_{A_2}^l(w_2)] \times [i_{A_1}^l(s_1) \wedge i_{L_1}^l(w_1 s_1) \wedge i_{L_2}^l(w_2) \wedge i_{L_2}^l(s_2 w_2)],$
 $(s_1, w_1)(s_2, w_2) \in E^\square.$
- (17) $f_B^l((s_1, s_2)(w_1, w_2)) = [f_{A_1}^l(s_1) \wedge f_{A_1}^l(w_1) \wedge f_{A_2}^l(s_2) \wedge f_{A_2}^l(w_2)] \times [f_{A_1}^l(s_1) \wedge f_{L_1}^l(w_1 s_1) \wedge f_{L_2}^l(w_2) \wedge f_{L_2}^l(s_2 w_2)],$
 $(s_1, w_1)(s_2, w_2) \in E^\square.$
- (18) $t_B^u((s_1, s_2)(w_1, w_2)) = [t_{A_1}^u(s_1) \wedge t_{A_1}^u(w_1) \wedge t_{A_2}^u(s_2) \wedge t_{A_2}^u(w_2)] \times [t_{A_1}^u(s_1) \wedge t_{L_1}^u(w_1 s_1) \wedge t_{L_2}^u(w_2) \wedge t_{L_2}^u(s_2 w_2)],$
 $(s_1, w_1)(s_2, w_2) \in E^\square.$
- (19) $i_B^u((s_1, s_2)(w_1, w_2)) = [i_{A_1}^u(s_1) \wedge i_{A_1}^u(w_1) \wedge i_{A_2}^u(s_2) \wedge i_{A_2}^u(w_2)] \times [i_{A_1}^u(s_1) \wedge i_{L_1}^u(w_1 s_1) \wedge i_{L_2}^u(w_2) \wedge i_{L_2}^u(s_2 w_2)],$
 $(s_1, w_1)(s_2, w_2) \in E^\square.$
- (20) $f_B^u((s_1, s_2)(w_1, w_2)) = [f_{A_1}^u(s_1) \wedge f_{A_1}^u(w_1) \wedge f_{A_2}^u(s_2) \wedge f_{A_2}^u(w_2)] \times [f_{A_1}^u(s_1) \wedge f_{L_1}^u(w_1 s_1) \wedge f_{L_2}^u(w_2) \wedge f_{L_2}^u(s_2 w_2)],$
 $(s_1, w_1)(s_2, w_2) \in E^\square.$

A. k -competition interval-valued neutrosophic graphs

We now discuss an extension of IVNC-graphs, called k -competition IVN-graphs.

Definition 2.18. The cardinality of an IVN-set A is denoted by

$$|A| = ([|A|_{t^l}, |A|_{t^u}], [|A|_{i^l}, |A|_{i^u}], [|A|_{f^l}, |A|_{f^u}]).$$

Where $[|A|_{t^l}, |A|_{t^u}]$, $[|A|_{i^l}, |A|_{i^u}]$ and $[|A|_{f^l}, |A|_{f^u}]$ represent the sum of truth-membership values, indeterminacy-membership values and falsity-membership values, respectively, of all the elements of A .

Example 2.19. The cardinality of an IVN-set $A = \{(a, [0.5, 0.7], [0.2, 0.8], [0.1, 0.3]), (b, [0.1, 0.2], [0.1, 0.5], [0.7, 0.9]), (c, [0.3, 0.5], [0.3, 0.8], [0.6, 0.9])\}$ in $X = \{a, b, c\}$ is

$$\begin{aligned} |A| &= ([|A|_{t^l}, |A|_{t^u}], [|A|_{i^l}, |A|_{i^u}], [|A|_{f^l}, |A|_{f^u}]) \\ &= ([0.9, 1.4], [0.6, 2.1], [1.4, 2.1]). \end{aligned}$$

We now discuss k -competition IVN-graphs.

Definition 2.20. Let k be a non-negative number. Then k -competition IVN-graph $\mathbb{C}_k(\vec{G})$ of an IVN-digraph $\vec{G} = (A, \vec{B})$ is an undirected IVN-graph $G = (A, B)$ which has same IVN-set of vertices as in $\vec{G}$ and has an interval-valued neutrosophic edge between two vertices $s, w \in X$ in $\mathbb{C}_k(\vec{G})$ if and only if $|(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))|_{t^l} > k$, $|(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))|_{t^u} > k$, $|(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))|_{i^l} > k$, $|(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))|_{i^u} > k$, $|(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))|_{f^l} > k$ and $|(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))|_{f^u} > k$. The interval-valued truth-membership value of edge (s, w) in $\mathbb{C}_k(\vec{G})$ is $t_B^l(s, w) = \frac{k_1^l - k}{k_1^l} [t_A^l(s) \wedge t_A^l(w)] h_1^l(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))$, where $k_1^l = |(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))|_{t^l}$ and $t_B^u(s, w) = \frac{k_1^u - k}{k_1^u} [t_A^u(s) \wedge t_A^u(w)] h_1^u(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))$, where $k_1^u = |(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))|_{t^u}$, the interval-valued indeterminacy-membership value of edge (s, w) in $\mathbb{C}_k(\vec{G})$ is $i_B^l(s, w) = \frac{k_2^l - k}{k_2^l} [i_A^l(s) \wedge i_A^l(w)] h_2^l(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))$, where $k_2^l = |(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))|_{i^l}$, and $i_B^u(s, w) = \frac{k_2^u - k}{k_2^u} [i_A^u(s) \wedge i_A^u(w)] h_2^u(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))$, where $k_2^u = |(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))|_{i^u}$, the interval-valued falsity-membership value of edge (s, w) in $\mathbb{C}_k(\vec{G})$ is $f_B^l(s, w) = \frac{k_3^l - k}{k_3^l} [f_A^l(s) \wedge f_A^l(w)] h_3^l(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))$, where $k_3^l = |(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))|_{f^l}$, and $f_B^u(s, w) = \frac{k_3^u - k}{k_3^u} [f_A^u(s) \wedge f_A^u(w)] h_3^u(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))$, where $k_3^u = |(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))|_{f^u}$.

Example 2.21. Consider an IVN-digraph $G = (A, \vec{B})$ on $X = \{s, w, a, b, c\}$, such that $A = \{(s, [0.4, 0.5], [0.5, 0.7], [0.8, 0.9]), (w, [0.6, 0.7], [0.4, 0.6], [0.2, 0.3]), (a, [0.2, 0.6], [0.3, 0.6], [0.2, 0.6]), (b, [0.2, 0.6], [0.1, 0.6], [0.2, 0.6]), (c, [0.2, 0.7], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.6])\}$, and $B = \{((s, a), [0.1, 0.4], [0.3, 0.6], [0.2, 0.6]), ((s, b), [0.2, 0.4], [0.1, 0.5], [0.2, 0.6]), ((s, c), [0.2, 0.5], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.6]), ((w, a), [0.2, 0.5], [0.2, 0.5], [0.2, 0.3]), ((w, b), [0.2, 0.6], [0.1, 0.6], [0.2, 0.3]), ((w, c), [0.2, 0.7], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.3])\}$, as shown in Fig. 5.

We calculate $\mathbb{N}^+(s) = \{(a, [0.1, 0.4], [0.3, 0.6], [0.2, 0.6]), (b, [0.2, 0.4], [0.1, 0.5], [0.2, 0.6]), (c, [0.2, 0.5], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.6])\}$ and $\mathbb{N}^+(w) = \{(a, [0.2, 0.5], [0.2, 0.5], [0.2, 0.3]), (b, [0.2, 0.6], [0.1, 0.6], [0.2, 0.3]), (c, [0.2, 0.7], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.3])\}$. Therefore, $\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w) = \{(a, [0.1, 0.4], [0.2, 0.5], [0.2, 0.3]), (b, [0.2, 0.4], [0.1, 0.5], [0.2, 0.3]), (c, [0.2, 0.5], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.3])\}$. So, $k_1^l = 0.5$, $k_1^u = 1.3$, $k_2^l = 0.6$, $k_2^u = 1.5$, $k_3^l = 0.6$ and $k_3^u = 0.9$. Let $k = 0.4$, then, $t_B^l(s, w) = 0.02$, $t_B^u(s, w) = 0.56$, $i_B^l(s, w) = 0.06$, $i_B^u(s, w) = 0.82$, $f_B^l(s, w) = 0.02$ and $f_B^u(s, w) = 0.11$. This graph is depicted in Fig. 6.

FIGURE 5. IVN-digraph

FIGURE 6. 0.4-Competition IVN-graph

Theorem 2.22. Let $\vec{G} = (A, \vec{B})$ be an IVN-digraph. If

$$\begin{aligned} h_1^l(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w)) &= 1, & h_2^l(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w)) &= 1, & h_3^l(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w)) &= 1, \\ h_1^u(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w)) &= 1, & h_2^u(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w)) &= 1, & h_3^u(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w)) &= 1, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} |(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))|_{t^l} &> 2k, & |(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))|_{i^l} &> 2k, & |(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))|_{f^l} &< 2k, \\ |(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))|_{t^u} &> 2k, & |(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))|_{i^u} &> 2k, & |(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))|_{f^u} &< 2k, \end{aligned}$$

Then the edge (s, w) is independent strong in $\mathbb{C}_k(\vec{G})$.

Proof. Let $\vec{G} = (A, \vec{B})$ be an IVN-digraph. Let $\mathbb{C}_k(\vec{G})$ be the corresponding k -competition IVN-graph.

If $h_1^l(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w)) = 1$ and $|(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))|_{t^l} > 2k$, then $k_1^l > 2k$. Thus,

$$t_B^l(s, w) = \frac{k_1^l - k}{k_1^l} [t_A^l(s) \wedge t_A^l(w)] h_1^l(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))$$

or, $t_B^l(s, w) = \frac{k_1^l - k}{k_1^l} [t_A^l(s) \wedge t_A^l(w)]$

$$\frac{t_B^l(s, w)}{[t_A^l(s) \wedge t_A^l(w)]} = \frac{k_1^l - k}{k_1^l} > 0.5.$$

If $h_1^u(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w)) = 1$ and $|(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))|_{t^u} > 2k$, then $k_1^u > 2k$. Thus,

$$t_B^u(s, w) = \frac{k_1^u - k}{k_1^u} [t_A^u(s) \wedge t_A^u(w)] h_1^u(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))$$

or, $t_B^u(s, w) = \frac{k_1^u - k}{k_1^u} [t_A^u(s) \wedge t_A^u(w)]$

$$\frac{t_B^u(s, w)}{[t_A^u(s) \wedge t_A^u(w)]} = \frac{k_1^u - k}{k_1^u} > 0.5.$$

If $h_2^l(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w)) = 1$ and $|(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))|_{i^l} > 2k$, then $k_2^l > 2k$. Thus,

$$i_B^l(s, w) = \frac{k_2^l - k}{k_2^l} [i_A^l(s) \wedge i_A^l(w)] h_2^l(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))$$

or, $i_B^l(s, w) = \frac{k_2^l - k}{k_2^l} [i_A^l(s) \wedge i_A^l(w)]$

$$\frac{i_B^l(s, w)}{[i_A^l(s) \wedge i_A^l(w)]} = \frac{k_2^l - k}{k_2^l} > 0.5.$$

If $h_2^u(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w)) = 1$ and $|(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))|_{i^u} > 2k$, then $k_2^u > 2k$. Thus,

$$i_B^u(s, w) = \frac{k_2^u - k}{k_2^u} [i_A^u(s) \wedge i_A^u(w)] h_2^u(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))$$

or, $i_B^u(s, w) = \frac{k_2^u - k}{k_2^u} [i_A^u(s) \wedge i_A^u(w)]$

$$\frac{i_B^u(s, w)}{[i_A^u(s) \wedge i_A^u(w)]} = \frac{k_2^u - k}{k_2^u} > 0.5.$$

If $h_3^l(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w)) = 1$ and $|(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))|_{f^l} < 2k$, then $k_3^l < 2k$. Thus,

$$f_B^l(s, w) = \frac{k_3^l - k}{k_3^l} [f_A^l(s) \wedge f_A^l(w)] h_3^l(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))$$

or, $f_B^l(s, w) = \frac{k_3^l - k}{k_3^l} [f_A^l(s) \wedge f_A^l(w)]$

$$\frac{f_B^l(s, w)}{[f_A^l(s) \wedge f_A^l(w)]} = \frac{k_3^l - k}{k_3^l} < 0.5.$$

If $h_3^u(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w)) = 1$ and $|\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w)|_{f^u} < 2k$, then $k_3^u < 2k$. Thus,

$$f_B^u(s, w) = \frac{k_3^u - k}{k_3^u} [f_A^u(s) \wedge f_A^u(w)] h_3^u(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))$$

$$\text{or, } f_B^u(s, w) = \frac{k_3^u - k}{k_3^u} [f_A^u(s) \wedge f_A^u(w)]$$

$$\frac{f_B^u(s, w)}{[f_A^u(s) \wedge f_A^u(w)]} = \frac{k_3^u - k}{k_3^u} < 0.5.$$

So, the edge (s, w) is independent strong in $\mathbb{C}_k(\vec{G})$. □

B. p -competition interval-valued neutrosophic graphs

We now define another extension of IVNC-graphs, called p -competition IVN-graphs.

Definition 2.23. The support of an IVN-set $A = (s, [t_A^l, t_A^u], [i_A^l, i_A^u], [f_A^l, f_A^u])$ in X is the subset of X defined by

$$\text{supp}(A) = \{s \in X : [t_A^l(s) \neq 0, t_A^u(s) \neq 0], [i_A^l(s) \neq 0, i_A^u(s) \neq 0], [f_A^l(s) \neq 1, f_A^u(s) \neq 1]\}$$

and $|\text{supp}(A)|$ is the number of elements in the set.

Example 2.24. The support of an IVN-set $A = \{(a, [0.5, 0.7], [0.2, 0.8], [0.1, 0.3]), (b, [0.1, 0.2], [0.1, 0.5], [0.7, 0.9]), (c, [0.3, 0.5], [0.3, 0.8], [0.6, 0.9]), (d, [0, 0], [0, 0], [1, 1])\}$ in $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ is $\text{supp}(A) = \{a, b, c\}$ and $|\text{supp}(A)| = 3$.

We now define p -competition IVN-graphs.

Definition 2.25. Let p be a positive integer. Then p -competition IVN-graph $\mathbb{C}^p(\vec{G})$ of the IVN-digraph $\vec{G} = (A, \vec{B})$ is an undirected IVN-graph $G = (A, B)$ which has same IVN-set of vertices as in $\vec{G}$ and has an interval-valued neutrosophic edge between two vertices $s, w \in X$ in $\mathbb{C}^p(\vec{G})$ if and only if $|\text{supp}(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))| \geq p$. The interval-valued truth-membership value of edge (s, w) in $\mathbb{C}^p(\vec{G})$ is $t_B^l(s, w) = \frac{(i-p)+1}{i} [t_A^l(s) \wedge t_A^l(w)] h_1^l(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))$, and $t_B^u(s, w) = \frac{(i-p)+1}{i} [t_A^u(s) \wedge t_A^u(w)] h_1^u(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))$, the interval-valued indeterminacy-membership value of edge (s, w) in $\mathbb{C}^p(\vec{G})$ is $i_B^l(s, w) = \frac{(i-p)+1}{i} [i_A^l(s) \wedge i_A^l(w)] h_2^l(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))$, and $i_B^u(s, w) = \frac{(i-p)+1}{i} [i_A^u(s) \wedge i_A^u(w)] h_2^u(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))$, the interval-valued falsity-membership value of edge (s, w) in $\mathbb{C}^p(\vec{G})$ is $f_B^l(s, w) = \frac{(i-p)+1}{i} [f_A^l(s) \wedge f_A^l(w)] h_3^l(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))$, and $f_B^u(s, w) = \frac{(i-p)+1}{i} [f_A^u(s) \wedge f_A^u(w)] h_3^u(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))$, where $i = |\text{supp}(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))|$.

Example 2.26. Consider an IVN-digraph $G = (A, \vec{B})$ on $X = \{s, w, a, b, c\}$, such that $A = \{(s, [0.4, 0.5], [0.5, 0.7], [0.8, 0.9]), (w, [0.6, 0.7], [0.4, 0.6], [0.2, 0.3]), (a, [0.2, 0.6], [0.3, 0.6], [0.2, 0.6]), (b, [0.2, 0.6], [0.1, 0.6], [0.2, 0.6]), (c, [0.2, 0.7], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.6])\}$, and $B = \{((s, a), [0.1, 0.4], [0.3, 0.6], [0.2, 0.6]), ((s, b), [0.2, 0.4], [0.1, 0.5], [0.2, 0.6]), ((s, c), [0.2, 0.5], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.6]), ((w, a), [0.2, 0.5], [0.2, 0.5], [0.2, 0.3]), ((w, b), [0.2, 0.6], [0.1, 0.6], [0.2, 0.3]), ((w, c), [0.2, 0.7], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.3])\}$, as shown in Fig. 7.

FIGURE 7. IVN-digraph

We calculate $\mathbb{N}^+(s) = \{(a, [0.1, 0.4], [0.3, 0.6], [0.2, 0.6]), (b, [0.2, 0.4], [0.1, 0.5], [0.2, 0.6]), (c, [0.2, 0.5], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.6])\}$ and $\mathbb{N}^+(w) = \{(a, [0.2, 0.5], [0.2, 0.5], [0.2, 0.3]), (b, [0.2, 0.6], [0.1, 0.6], [0.2, 0.3]), (c, [0.2, 0.7], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.3])\}$. Therefore, $\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w) = \{(a, [0.1, 0.4], [0.2, 0.5], [0.2, 0.3]), (b, [0.2, 0.4], [0.1, 0.5], [0.2, 0.3]), (c, [0.2, 0.5], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.3])\}$. Now, $i = |\text{supp}(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))| = 3$. For $p = 3$, we have, $t_B^l(s, w) = 0.02$, $t_B^u(s, w) = 0.08$, $i_B^l(s, w) = 0.04$, $i_B^u(s, w) = 0.1$, $f_B^l(s, w) = 0.01$ and $f_B^u(s, w) = 0.03$. This graph is depicted in Fig. 8.

FIGURE 8. 3-Competition IVN-graph

We state the following theorem without its proof.

Theorem 2.27. Let $\vec{G} = (A, \vec{B})$ be an IVN-digraph. If

$$h_1^l(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w)) = 1, \quad h_2^l(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w)) = 1, \quad h_3^l(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w)) = 0,$$

$$h_1^u(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w)) = 1, \quad h_2^u(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w)) = 1, \quad h_3^u(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w)) = 0,$$

in $\mathbb{C}^{\lfloor \frac{i}{2} \rfloor}(\vec{G})$, then the edge (s, w) is strong, where $i = |\text{supp}(\mathbb{N}^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}^+(w))|$. (Note that for any real number s , $\lfloor s \rfloor =$ greatest integer not exceeding s .)

C. m -step interval-valued neutrosophic competition graphs

We now define another extension of IVNC-graph known as m -step IVNC-graph. We will use the following notations:

$P_{s,w}^m$: An interval-valued neutrosophic path of length m from s to w .

$\vec{P}_{s,w}^m$: A directed interval-valued neutrosophic path of length m from s to w .

$\mathbb{N}_m^+(s)$: m -step interval-valued neutrosophic out-neighbourhood of vertex s .

$\mathbb{N}_m^-(s)$: m -step interval-valued neutrosophic in-neighbourhood of vertex s .

$\mathbb{N}_m(s)$: m -step interval-valued neutrosophic neighbourhood of vertex s .

$\mathbb{N}_m(G)$: m -step interval-valued neutrosophic neighbourhood graph of the IVN-graph G .

$\mathbb{C}_m(\vec{G})$: m -step IVNC-graph of the IVN-digraph $\vec{G}$.

Definition 2.28. Suppose $\vec{G} = (A, \vec{B})$ is an IVN-digraph. The m -step IVN-digraph of $\vec{G}$ is denoted by $\vec{G}_m = (A, B)$, where IVN-set of vertices of $\vec{G}$ is same with IVN-set of vertices of $\vec{G}_m$ and has an edge between s and w in $\vec{G}_m$ if and only if there exists an interval-valued neutrosophic directed path $\vec{P}_{s,w}^m$ in $\vec{G}$.

Definition 2.29. The m -step interval-valued neutrosophic out-neighbourhood (IVN-out-neighbourhood) of vertex s of an IVN-digraph $\vec{G} = (A, \vec{B})$ is IVN-set

$$\mathbb{N}_m^+(s) = (X_s^+, [t_s^{(l)+}, t_s^{(u)+}], [i_s^{(l)+}, i_s^{(u)+}], [f_s^{(l)+}, f_s^{(u)+}]), \quad \text{where}$$

$X_s^+ = \{w \mid \text{there exists a directed interval-valued neutrosophic path of length } m \text{ from } s \text{ to } w, \vec{P}_{s,w}^m\}$, $t_s^{(l)+} : X_s^+ \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $t_s^{(u)+} : X_s^+ \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $i_s^{(l)+} : X_s^+ \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $i_s^{(u)+} : X_s^+ \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $f_s^{(l)+} : X_s^+ \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $f_s^{(u)+} : X_s^+ \rightarrow [0, 1]$ are defined by $t_s^{(l)+} = \min\{t^l(s_1, s_2) \mid (s_1, s_2) \text{ is an edge of } \vec{P}_{s,w}^m\}$, $t_s^{(u)+} = \min\{t^u(s_1, s_2) \mid (s_1, s_2) \text{ is an edge of } \vec{P}_{s,w}^m\}$, $i_s^{(l)+} = \min\{i^l(s_1, s_2) \mid (s_1, s_2) \text{ is an edge of } \vec{P}_{s,w}^m\}$, $i_s^{(u)+} = \min\{i^u(s_1, s_2) \mid (s_1, s_2) \text{ is an edge of } \vec{P}_{s,w}^m\}$, $f_s^{(l)+} = \min\{f^l(s_1, s_2) \mid (s_1, s_2) \text{ is an edge of } \vec{P}_{s,w}^m\}$, $f_s^{(u)+} = \min\{f^u(s_1, s_2) \mid (s_1, s_2) \text{ is an edge of } \vec{P}_{s,w}^m\}$, respectively.

Example 2.30. Consider an IVN-digraph $G = (A, \vec{B})$ on $X = \{s, w, a, b, c, d\}$, such that $A = \{(s, [0.4, 0.5], [0.5, 0.7], [0.8, 0.9])$, $(w, [0.6, 0.7], [0.4, 0.6], [0.2, 0.3])$, $(a, [0.2, 0.6], [0.3, 0.6], [0.2, 0.6])$, $(b, [0.2, 0.6], [0.1, 0.6], [0.2, 0.6])$, $(c, [0.2, 0.7], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.6])$, $d([0.2, 0.6], [0.3, 0.6], [0.2, 0.6])\}$, and $B = \{((s, a), [0.1, 0.4], [0.3, 0.6], [0.2, 0.6])$, $((a, c), [0.2, 0.6], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.6])$, $((a, d), [0.2, 0.6], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.4])$, $((w, b), [0.2, 0.6], [0.1, 0.6], [0.2, 0.3])$, $((b, c), [0.2, 0.4], [0.1, 0.2], [0.1, 0.3])$, $((b, d), [0.1, 0.3], [0.1, 0.2], [0.2, 0.4])\}$, as shown in Fig. 9.

FIGURE 9. IVN-digraph

We calculate 2-step IVN-out-neighbourhoods as, $\mathbb{N}_2^+(s) = \{(c, [0.1, 0.4], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.6]), (d, [0.1, 0.4], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.4])\}$ and $\mathbb{N}_2^+(w) = \{(c, [0.2, 0.4], [0.1, 0.2], [0.1, 0.3]), (d, [0.1, 0.3], [0.1, 0.2], [0.2, 0.3])\}$.

Definition 2.31. The m -step interval-valued neutrosophic in-neighbourhood (IVN-in-neighbourhood) of vertex s of an IVN-digraph $\vec{G} = (A, \vec{B})$ is IVN-set

$$\mathbb{N}_m^-(s) = (X_s^-, [t_s^{(l)-}, t_s^{(u)-}], [i_s^{(l)-}, i_s^{(u)-}], [f_s^{(l)-}, f_s^{(u)-}]), \quad \text{where}$$

$X_s^- = \{w \mid \text{there exists a directed interval-valued neutrosophic path of length } m \text{ from } w \text{ to } s, \vec{P}_{w,s}^m\}$, $t_s^{(l)-} : X_s^- \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $t_s^{(u)-} : X_s^- \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $i_s^{(l)-} : X_s^- \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $i_s^{(u)-} : X_s^- \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $f_s^{(l)-} : X_s^- \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $f_s^{(u)-} : X_s^- \rightarrow [0, 1]$ are defined by $t_s^{(l)-} = \min\{t^l(\overrightarrow{s_1, s_2})\}$, (s_1, s_2) is an edge of $\vec{P}_{w,s}^m$, $t_s^{(u)-} = \min\{t^u(\overrightarrow{s_1, s_2})\}$, (s_1, s_2) is an edge of $\vec{P}_{w,s}^m$, $i_s^{(l)-} = \min\{i^l(\overrightarrow{s_1, s_2})\}$, (s_1, s_2) is an edge of $\vec{P}_{w,s}^m$, $i_s^{(u)-} = \min\{i^u(\overrightarrow{s_1, s_2})\}$, (s_1, s_2) is an edge of $\vec{P}_{w,s}^m$, $f_s^{(l)-} = \min\{f^l(\overrightarrow{s_1, s_2})\}$, (s_1, s_2) is an edge of $\vec{P}_{w,s}^m$, $f_s^{(u)-} = \min\{f^u(\overrightarrow{s_1, s_2})\}$, (s_1, s_2) is an edge of $\vec{P}_{w,s}^m$, respectively.

Example 2.32. Consider an IVN-digraph $G = (A, \vec{B})$ on $X = \{s, w, a, b, c, d\}$, such that $A = \{(s, [0.4, 0.5], [0.5, 0.7], [0.8, 0.9]), (w, [0.6, 0.7], [0.4, 0.6], [0.2, 0.3]), (a, [0.2, 0.6], [0.3, 0.6], [0.2, 0.6]), (b, [0.2, 0.6], [0.1, 0.6], [0.2, 0.6]), (c, [0.2, 0.7], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.6]), (d, [0.2, 0.6], [0.3, 0.6], [0.2, 0.6])\}$, and $B = \{((s, a), [0.1, 0.4], [0.3, 0.6], [0.2, 0.6]), ((a, c), [0.2, 0.6], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.6]), ((a, d), [0.2, 0.6], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.4]), ((w, b), [0.2, 0.6], [0.1, 0.6], [0.2, 0.3]), ((b, c), [0.2, 0.4], [0.1, 0.2], [0.1, 0.3]), ((b, d), [0.1, 0.3], [0.1, 0.2], [0.2, 0.4])\}$, as shown in Fig. 10.

FIGURE 10. IVN-digraph

We calculate 2-step IVN-in-neighbourhoods as, $\mathbb{N}_2^-(s) = \{(c, [0.1, 0.4], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.6]), (d, [0.1, 0.4], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.4])\}$ and $\mathbb{N}_2^-(w) = \{(c, [0.2, 0.4], [0.1, 0.2], [0.1, 0.3]), (d, [0.1, 0.3], [0.1, 0.2], [0.2, 0.3])\}$.

Definition 2.33. Suppose $\vec{G} = (A, \vec{B})$ is an IVN-digraph. The m -step IVNC-graph of IVN-digraph $\vec{G}$ is denoted by $\mathbb{C}_m(\vec{G}) = (A, B)$ which has same IVN-set of vertices as in $\vec{G}$ and has an edge between two vertices $s, w \in X$ in $\mathbb{C}_m(\vec{G})$ if and only if $(\mathbb{N}_m^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}_m^+(w))$ is a non-empty IVN-set in $\vec{G}$. The interval-valued truth-membership value of edge (s, w) in $\mathbb{C}_m(\vec{G})$ is $t_B^l(s, w) = [t_A^l(s) \wedge t_A^l(w)]h_1^l(\mathbb{N}_m^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}_m^+(w))$, and $t_B^u(s, w) = [t_A^u(s) \wedge t_A^u(w)]h_1^u(\mathbb{N}_m^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}_m^+(w))$, the interval-valued indeterminacy-membership value of edge (s, w) in $\mathbb{C}_m(\vec{G})$ is $i_B^l(s, w) = [i_A^l(s) \wedge i_A^l(w)]h_2^l(\mathbb{N}_m^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}_m^+(w))$, and $i_B^u(s, w) = [i_A^u(s) \wedge i_A^u(w)]h_2^u(\mathbb{N}_m^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}_m^+(w))$, the interval-valued falsity-membership value of edge (s, w) in $\mathbb{C}_m(\vec{G})$ is $f_B^l(s, w) = [f_A^l(s) \wedge f_A^l(w)]h_3^l(\mathbb{N}_m^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}_m^+(w))$, and $f_B^u(s, w) = [f_A^u(s) \wedge f_A^u(w)]h_3^u(\mathbb{N}_m^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}_m^+(w))$.

The 2-step IVNC-graph is illustrated by the following example.

Example 2.34. Consider an IVN-digraph $G = (A, \vec{B})$ on $X = \{s, w, a, b, c, d\}$, such that $A = \{(s, [0.4, 0.5], [0.5, 0.7], [0.8, 0.9]), (w, [0.6, 0.7], [0.4, 0.6], [0.2, 0.3]), (a, [0.2, 0.6], [0.3, 0.6], [0.2, 0.6]), (b, [0.2, 0.6], [0.1, 0.6], [0.2, 0.6]), (c, [0.2, 0.7], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.6]), (d, [0.2, 0.6], [0.3, 0.6], [0.2, 0.6])\}$, and $B = \{((s, a), [0.1, 0.4], [0.3, 0.6], [0.2, 0.6]), ((a, c), [0.2, 0.6], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.6]), ((a, d), [0.2, 0.6], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.4]), ((w, b), [0.2, 0.6], [0.1, 0.6], [0.2, 0.3]), ((b, c), [0.2, 0.4], [0.1, 0.2], [0.1, 0.3]), ((b, d), [0.1, 0.3], [0.1, 0.2], [0.2, 0.4])\}$, as shown in Fig. 11.

FIGURE 11. IVN-digraph

We calculate $\mathbb{N}_2^+(s) = \{(c, [0.1, 0.4], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.6]), (d, [0.1, 0.4], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.4])\}$ and $\mathbb{N}_2^+(w) = \{(c, [0.2, 0.4], [0.1, 0.2], [0.1, 0.3]), (d, [0.1, 0.3], [0.1, 0.2], [0.2, 0.3])\}$. Therefore, $\mathbb{N}_2^+(s) \cap \mathbb{N}_2^+(w) = \{(c, [0.1, 0.4], [0.1, 0.2], [0.2, 0.6]), (d, [0.1, 0.3], [0.1, 0.2], [0.2, 0.4])\}$. Thus, $t_B^l(s, w) = 0.04$, $t_B^u(s, w) = 0.20$, $i_B^l(s, w) = 0.04$, $i_B^u(s, w) = 0.12$, $f_B^l(s, w) = 0.04$ and $f_B^u(s, w) = 0.12$. This graph is depicted in Fig. 12.

FIGURE 12. 2-Step IVNC-graph

If a predator s attacks one prey w , then the linkage is shown by an edge $\overrightarrow{(s, w)}$ in an IVN-digraph. But, if predator needs help of many other mediators $s_1, s_2, \dots, s_{m-1}$, then linkage among them is shown by interval-valued neutrosophic directed path $\overrightarrow{P}_{s,w}^m$ in an IVN-digraph. So, m -step prey in an IVN-digraph is represented by a vertex which is the m -step out-neighbourhood of some vertices. Now, the strength of an IVNC-graphs is defined below.

Definition 2.35. Let $\vec{G} = (A, \vec{B})$ be an IVN-digraph. Let w be a common vertex of m -step out-neighbourhoods of vertices $s_1, s_2, \dots, s_l$. Also, let $\vec{B}_1^l(u_1, v_1), \vec{B}_1^l(u_2, v_2), \dots, \vec{B}_1^l(u_r, v_r)$ and $\vec{B}_1^u(u_1, v_1), \vec{B}_1^u(u_2, v_2), \dots, \vec{B}_1^u(u_r, v_r)$ be the minimum interval-valued truth-membership values, $\vec{B}_2^l(u_1, v_1), \vec{B}_2^l(u_2, v_2), \dots, \vec{B}_2^l(u_r, v_r)$ and $\vec{B}_2^u(u_1, v_1), \vec{B}_2^u(u_2, v_2), \dots, \vec{B}_2^u(u_r, v_r)$ be the minimum indeterminacy-membership

values, $\vec{B}_3^l(u_1, v_1), \vec{B}_3^l(u_2, v_2), \dots, \vec{B}_3^l(u_r, v_r)$ and $\vec{B}_3^u(u_1, v_1), \vec{B}_3^u(u_2, v_2), \dots, \vec{B}_3^u(u_r, v_r)$ be the maximum false-membership values, of edges of the paths $\vec{P}_{s_1, w}^m, \vec{P}_{s_2, w}^m, \dots, \vec{P}_{s_r, w}^m$, respectively. The m -step prey $w \in X$ is strong prey if

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{B}_1^l(u_i, v_i) > 0.5, \quad \vec{B}_2^l(u_i, v_i) > 0.5, \quad \vec{B}_3^l(u_i, v_i) < 0.5, \\ \vec{B}_1^u(u_i, v_i) > 0.5, \quad \vec{B}_2^u(u_i, v_i) > 0.5, \quad \vec{B}_3^u(u_i, v_i) < 0.5, \text{ for all } i = 1, 2, \dots, r. \end{aligned}$$

The strength of the prey w can be measured by the mapping $S : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$, such that:

$$\begin{aligned} S(w) = \frac{1}{r} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^r [\vec{B}_1^l(u_i, v_i)] + \sum_{i=1}^r [\vec{B}_1^u(u_i, v_i)] + \sum_{i=1}^r [\vec{B}_2^l(u_i, v_i)] \right. \\ \left. + \sum_{i=1}^r [\vec{B}_2^u(u_i, v_i)] - \sum_{i=1}^r [\vec{B}_3^l(u_i, v_i)] - \sum_{i=1}^r [\vec{B}_3^u(u_i, v_i)] \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Example 2.36. Consider an IVN-digraph $\vec{G} = (A, \vec{B})$ as shown in Fig. 11, the strength of the prey c is equal to

$$\frac{(0.2 + 0.2) + (0.6 + 0.4) + (0.1 + 0.1) + (0.6 + 0.2) - (0.2 + 0.1) - (0.3 + 0.3)}{2} = 1.5 > 0.5.$$

Hence, c is strong 2-step prey.

We state the following theorem without its proof.

Theorem 2.37. *If a prey w of $\vec{G} = (A, \vec{B})$ is strong, then the strength of w , $S(w) > 0.5$.*

Remark 2.38. The converse of the above theorem is not true, i.e. if $S(w) > 0.5$, then all preys may not be strong. This can be explained as:

Let $S(w) > 0.5$ for a prey w in $\vec{G}$. So,

$$\begin{aligned} S(w) = \frac{1}{r} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^r [\vec{B}_1^l(u_i, v_i)] + \sum_{i=1}^r [\vec{B}_1^u(u_i, v_i)] + \sum_{i=1}^r [\vec{B}_2^l(u_i, v_i)] \right. \\ \left. + \sum_{i=1}^r [\vec{B}_2^u(u_i, v_i)] - \sum_{i=1}^r [\vec{B}_3^l(u_i, v_i)] - \sum_{i=1}^r [\vec{B}_3^u(u_i, v_i)] \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^r [\vec{B}_1^l(u_i, v_i)] + \sum_{i=1}^r [\vec{B}_1^u(u_i, v_i)] + \sum_{i=1}^r [\vec{B}_2^l(u_i, v_i)] \right. \\ \left. + \sum_{i=1}^r [\vec{B}_2^u(u_i, v_i)] - \sum_{i=1}^r [\vec{B}_3^l(u_i, v_i)] - \sum_{i=1}^r [\vec{B}_3^u(u_i, v_i)] \right\} > \frac{r}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

This result does not necessarily imply that

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{B}_1^l(u_i, v_i) > 0.5, \quad \vec{B}_2^l(u_i, v_i) > 0.5, \quad \vec{B}_3^l(u_i, v_i) < 0.5, \\ \vec{B}_1^u(u_i, v_i) > 0.5, \quad \vec{B}_2^u(u_i, v_i) > 0.5, \quad \vec{B}_3^u(u_i, v_i) < 0.5, \end{aligned}$$

for all $i = 1, 2, \dots, r$.

Since, all edges of the directed paths $\vec{P}_{s_1, w}^m, \vec{P}_{s_2, w}^m, \dots, \vec{P}_{s_r, w}^m$, are not strong. So, the converse of the above statement is not true i.e., if $S(w) > 0.5$, the prey w of $\vec{G}$ may not be strong. Now, m -step interval-valued neutrosophic neighbourhood graphs are defines below.

Definition 2.39. The m -step IVN-out-neighbourhood of vertex s of an IVN-digraph $\vec{G} = (A, \vec{B})$ is IVN-set

$$\mathbb{N}_m(s) = (X_s, [t_s^l, t_s^u], [i_s^l, i_s^u], [f_s^l, f_s^u]), \quad \text{where}$$

$X_s = \{w \mid \text{there exists a directed interval-valued neutrosophic path of length } m \text{ from } s \text{ to } w, \mathbb{P}_{s, w}^m\}$, $t_s^l : X_s \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $t_s^u : X_s \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $i_s^l : X_s \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $i_s^u : X_s \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $f_s^l : X_s \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $f_s^u : X_s \rightarrow [0, 1]$, are defined by $t_s^l = \min\{t^l(s_1, s_2), (s_1, s_2) \text{ is an edge of } \mathbb{P}_{s, w}^m\}$, $t_s^u = \min\{t^u(s_1, s_2), (s_1, s_2) \text{ is an edge of } \mathbb{P}_{s, w}^m\}$, $i_s^l = \min\{i^l(s_1, s_2), (s_1, s_2) \text{ is an edge of } \mathbb{P}_{s, w}^m\}$, $i_s^u = \min\{i^u(s_1, s_2), (s_1, s_2) \text{ is an edge of } \mathbb{P}_{s, w}^m\}$, $f_s^l = \min\{f^l(s_1, s_2), (s_1, s_2) \text{ is an edge of } \mathbb{P}_{s, w}^m\}$, $f_s^u = \min\{f^u(s_1, s_2), (s_1, s_2) \text{ is an edge of } \mathbb{P}_{s, w}^m\}$, respectively.

Definition 2.40. Suppose $G = (A, B)$ is an IVN-graph. Then m -step interval-valued neutrosophic neighbourhood graph $\mathbb{N}_m(G)$ is defined by $\mathbb{N}_m(G) = (A, \vec{B})$ where $A = ([A_1^l, A_1^u], [A_2^l, A_2^u], [A_3^l, A_3^u])$, $\vec{B} = ([\vec{B}_1^l, \vec{B}_1^u], [\vec{B}_2^l, \vec{B}_2^u], [\vec{B}_3^l, \vec{B}_3^u])$, $\vec{B}_1^l : X \times X \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $\vec{B}_1^u : X \times X \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $\vec{B}_2^l : X \times X \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $\vec{B}_2^u : X \times X \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $\vec{B}_3^l : X \times X \rightarrow [0, 1]$, and $\vec{B}_3^u : X \times X \rightarrow [0, -1]$ are such that:

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{B}_1^l(s, w) &= A_1^l(s) \wedge A_1^l(w) h_1^l(\mathbb{N}_m(s) \cap \mathbb{N}_m(w)), \\ \vec{B}_2^l(s, w) &= A_2^l(s) \wedge A_2^l(w) h_2^l(\mathbb{N}_m(s) \cap \mathbb{N}_m(w)), \\ \vec{B}_3^l(s, w) &= A_3^l(s) \wedge A_3^l(w) h_3^l(\mathbb{N}_m(s) \cap \mathbb{N}_m(w)), \\ \vec{B}_1^u(s, w) &= A_1^u(s) \wedge A_1^u(w) h_1^u(\mathbb{N}_m(s) \cap \mathbb{N}_m(w)), \\ \vec{B}_2^u(s, w) &= A_2^u(s) \wedge A_2^u(w) h_2^u(\mathbb{N}_m(s) \cap \mathbb{N}_m(w)), \\ \vec{B}_3^u(s, w) &= A_3^u(s) \wedge A_3^u(w) h_3^u(\mathbb{N}_m(s) \cap \mathbb{N}_m(w)), \end{aligned}$$

respectively.

We state the following theorems without thier proofs.

Theorem 2.41. *If all preys of $\vec{G} = (A, \vec{B})$ are strong, then all edges of $\mathbb{C}_m(\vec{G}) = (A, B)$ are strong.*

A relation is established between m -step IVNC-graph of an IVN-digraph and IVNC-graph of m -step IVN-digraph.

Theorem 2.42. *If $\vec{G}$ is an IVN-digraph and $\vec{G}_m$ is the m -step IVN-digraph of $\vec{G}$, then $\mathbb{C}(\vec{G}_m) = \mathbb{C}_m(\vec{G})$.*

Theorem 2.43. *Let $\vec{G} = (A, \vec{B})$ be an IVN-digraph. If $m > |X|$ then $\mathbb{C}_m(\vec{G}) = (A, B)$ has no edge.*

Theorem 2.44. *If all the edges of IVN-digraph $\vec{G} = (A, \vec{B})$ are independent strong, then all the edges of $\mathbb{C}_m(\vec{G})$ are independent strong.*

3. CONCLUSIONS

Graph theory is an enjoyable playground for the research of proof techniques in discrete mathematics. There are many applications of graph theory in different fields. We have introduced IVNC-graphs and k -competition IVN-graphs, p -competition IVN-graphs and m -step IVNC-graphs as the generalized structures of IVNC-graphs. We have described interval-valued neutrosophic open and closed-neighbourhood. Also we have established some results related to them. We aim to extend our research work to (1) Interval-valued fuzzy rough graphs; (2) Interval-valued fuzzy rough hypergraphs, (3) Interval-valued fuzzy rough neutrosophic graphs, and (4) Decision support systems based on IVN-graphs.

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